

21 **Abstract**

22 Saponifiable lipids (SLs), rich in eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA), were extracted and purified
23 from *Nannochloropsis gaditana* biomass. Firstly, the SLs were extracted using ethanol (96%
24 v/v). The influence of the following operational variables was studied: water content of the
25 wet biomass, solvent/biomass ratio, homogenization pressure and temperature. SL yields of
26 92-99 wt% and 80-90 wt% were achieved from dry and wet biomass, respectively, under
27 various operational conditions from batches with different SL contents and lipid profiles.
28 These SLs were extracted with only a 20-22 wt% purity, which was increased to 42% (100
29 wt% yield) by extracting the SLs with hexane. In this hexane extraction step, it was important
30 to extract the SLs from a highly concentrated hydroethanolic solution. The SL purity was
31 further increased to 95 wt% by acetone crystallization. Throughout this extraction-purification
32 process, SLs were fractionated into neutral lipids, glycolipids and phospholipids - neutral
33 lipids were recovered with higher yields than were glycolipids and phospholipids. The energy
34 consumption per unit mass of extracted lipids was estimated, along with the solvent recovery,
35 and compared for the dry and wet methods. When wet biomass was used, the presence of
36 water significantly increased the energy required for ethanol recovery, canceling the
37 advantage of eliminating lyophilization when using wet biomass.

38

39 **Keywords:** Lipid extraction, Microalgae, Lipid purification, Low-toxicity organic solvents,
40 Energy consumption evaluation.

41

42 **1. Introduction**

43 Microalgae are considered one of the most promising feedstocks for the sustainable
44 supply of both food and non-food products. They can potentially revolutionize a large
45 number of biotechnology areas, including biofuels, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, nutrition and
46 food additives, aquaculture and pollution prevention. As a source of functional foods, they are
47 a priority area in algal technology (Mata, Martins & Caetano, 2010; Batista, Gouveia,
48 Bandarra, Franco & Raimundo, 2013; Draaisma, Wijffels, Slegers, Brentner, Roy & Barbosa,
49 2013).

50 Microalgae are the initial ARA, EPA and DHA (arachidonic, eicosapentaenoic and
51 docosahexaenoic acids) producers in the marine food chain and these could be used as the raw
52 material to supply long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (LC-PUFAs) at the recommended
53 human dietary levels (Adarme, Lim, Timmins, Vernen, Li & Schenk, 2012; Martins *et al.*,
54 2013; Geels, Bishop & Ferguson, 2013). Based on both the total lipid and LC-PUFA contents,
55 and considering the ease of cultivation, the microalgae which hold the most promise for
56 commercialization are probably *Nannochloropsis* and *Phaeodactylum* as a source of EPA, and
57 *Isochrysis* as a source of DHA.

58 Significant advances have been made in the culture conditions necessary to generate
59 biomass that is highly rich in lipids. However, as part of the downstream process, lipid
60 extraction continues to be a significant challenge to the commercial production of microalgal
61 oil, even though a multitude of extraction methods have been described in the literature.
62 Efficient lipid extraction is largely dependent on the polarity of the organic solvent or solvent
63 mixture used. In general, solvent mixtures containing a polar and a non-polar solvent can
64 extract a greater amount of lipids. For example, a combination of chloroform (non-polar),
65 methanol (polar) and water, known as the Bligh & Dyer method, has been used for lipid
66 extraction from a wide range of biological samples. However, concerns about biosafety issues

67 using extraction solvents has driven the demand for biocompatible and less or non-toxic
68 solvents (Li *et al.*, 2014).

69 The extraction of fatty acid-containing lipids or saponifiable lipids (SLs) from
70 microalgae with high yields and especially high purities is a difficult problem which has not
71 yet been totally resolved due to the complex composition of microalgae and their lipid
72 fraction. Some of the solvents or mixtures of solvents used may not only extract lipids but
73 also non-lipid components such as carbohydrates or proteins.

74 Few authors include in their results the non-lipid co-extraction that takes place in the
75 microalgal biomass extraction process. Among them, Ryckebosch *et al.* (2013) tested
76 different solvent systems reporting lipid and non-lipid extraction yields, which allowed them
77 to calculate the purity of the lipid extract. In this study, the best results were obtained from the
78 chloroform /methanol, dichloromethane /ethanol, hexane /isopropanol and ethanol systems.
79 Discarding the halogenated systems, extraction with ethanol gave the highest extraction yield,
80 although only 60% of the extract consisted of lipids (a purity of 60%).

81 Ethanol is a polar, cheap and safe solvent and has a strong affinity toward the lipid
82 complexes, which implies that lipids can be extracted efficiently. Moreover, ethanol is
83 approved as a safe and ecofriendly solvent, suggesting that the residual biomass could be used
84 for producing foodstuffs and food ingredients after lipid extraction. It has been extensively
85 used in our laboratory for lipid extraction from lyophilized microalgal biomass providing high
86 SL recoveries (Molina, Robles, Giménez, Sánchez García & García, 1994; Ramírez, Esteban,
87 Robles, Ación, González & Molina, 2007).

88 Recently, Yang *et al.* (2015) tested lipid extraction with ethanol at room temperature
89 from wet marine *Chlorella* sp. 442, *Chlorella* sp. 725 and *Picochlorum* sp. 802, obtaining
90 lipid extraction yields, lipid profiles, and fatty acid distributions similar to those of the Bligh
91 & Dyer method. Castejón & Señoráns (2019) have also performed lipid extraction from wet

92 *Nannochloropsis gaditana* biomass using pressurized liquids with ethanol at 120 °C. The
93 authors focus on the lipid yield (12.1% of dry weight) and compare it with the Folch method
94 (15.0%). None of them reported the purity of the obtained extract or the non-lipid co-
95 extraction that occurred, although Yang *et al.* recognized that crude lipids might contain
96 several non-lipids (proteins that strongly bond to lipids and carbohydrates) and used hexane to
97 try to remove them, according to the method reported by Ramírez Fajardo *et al.* (2007).

98 On the other hand, the use of dry or lyophilized biomass is related to the lipid
99 extraction costs. It has been reported that drying accounted for up to 84.9% of the total energy
100 input for the lipid extraction process (Lardon, Helias, Sialve, Steyer & Bernard, 2009; Patil *et*
101 *al.* 2012). For this reason, many research works have studied lipid extraction from wet
102 biomass. Nonetheless, the algal paste obtained by centrifugal dewatering contains more than
103 70-80% water and this residual water hinders the extraction of lipids from the cells, resulting
104 in a decrease in lipid extraction efficiency (Halim, Danquah & Webley, 2012). Thus, it is
105 usual to apply a pretreatment to the microalgal biomass such as sonication (Wang & Wang,
106 2012), osmotic shock (Yoo, Park, Kim, Choi & Yang, 2012) or high-pressure homogenization
107 (Jiménez Callejón *et al.*, 2014) prior to lipid extraction in order to increase solvent
108 accessibility to the microalgal lipids.

109 Furthermore, few authors have compared the energy consumption of the proposed
110 lipid extraction processes by considering the solvent recovery. Tanzi, Vian & Chemat (2013)
111 calculated the energy required to obtain lipids from dry biomass using Soxhlet extraction
112 (8.84 kWh per g of extracted lipid) and from wet biomass using simultaneous distillation and
113 a terpene extraction process (2.15 kWh/g). Du, Schuur, Kersten & Brilman (2015) compared
114 the total energy consumptions for lipid extraction from *Desmodesmus* sp. using hexane; these
115 were 37.2 and 25.1 MJ/Kg of lipids for the dry and wet method, respectively.

116 Therefore, the purpose of this study was to obtain EPA-rich saponifiable lipids, with
117 high yields and especially high purities, both from lyophilized and wet *Nannochloropsis*
118 *gaditana* microalgal biomass, using organic solvents that are permitted in the food industry.
119 Importantly, the present research also compares the energy consumption for the drying, lipid
120 extraction and solvent recovery processes of both the dry and wet methods. The procedure
121 used consists of three steps: 1) direct lipid extraction from the microalgal biomass using
122 ethanol (96%), 2) purification of these lipids through a second extraction step using hexane
123 and 3) final saponifiable lipid purification using low-temperature acetone crystallization.

124 **2. Materials and methods**

125 *2.1. Microalgal biomass and chemicals*

126 Two batches of wet biomass from the marine microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana* Lubián
127 CCMP 527 were used in this work. The batches were grown in two pilot-scale tubular
128 photobioreactors, under different culture conditions, at the University of Almería facilities.
129 Batch 1 was cultivated in continuous mode, with standard Algal medium (8.0 mM nitrate) at a
130 dilution rate of 0.3 day⁻¹. Batch 2 was initially cultivated under the same conditions, but once
131 steady state was reached, the culture was centrifuged and the pellet was resuspended in
132 nitrate-free culture medium (nitrogen-starvation conditions). Afterwards, the reactor was
133 operated in batch mode for 12 days (San Pedro, González, Acién & Molina, 2013). Both
134 biomass batches were then harvested by centrifugation and then stored at -20 °C until use.
135 After this first centrifugation, the wet biomass contained 86.0 ± 0.1 wt% of water. To obtain
136 biomass batches with a lower water content (76.0 ± 0.1 wt% water), the wet biomass
137 harvested was again centrifuged at 7000 rpm for 10 min (Sartorius Sigma Laboratory
138 Centrifuge 4–15, Germany). In addition, lyophilized biomass was obtained for use in the lipid
139 extraction experiments. The dry weight content of the wet biomass samples was determined in

140 triplicate by measuring the weight ratio between samples after and before lyophilization.

141 Table 1 shows the SL content and fatty-acid composition of the two biomass batches used in
142 this study.

143 The organic solvents used (ethanol 96% v/v, n-hexane and acetone) were of analytical
144 grade (Panreac S.A., Barcelona, Spain). All reagents used in the analytical determinations
145 were also of analytical grade. Standards were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO,
146 USA) and were used without further purification.

147

148 *2.2. Extraction of crude microalgal oil*

149 The lipid extraction was carried out by treating different amounts of wet (76 and 86 wt%
150 water) and lyophilized biomass with 50 mL ethanol (96% v/v), so that the solvent
151 volume/equivalent dry biomass ratios tested were 5, 10, 20, 40 and 60 mL of ethanol (96%
152 v/v)/g dry biomass (db). The extractions were carried out in 250 mL bottles (in a nitrogen
153 atmosphere) with screw caps, placed in an orbital shaker (Inkubator 1000, Unimax 1010
154 Heidolph, Klein, Germany), agitated at 200 rpm, at different temperatures (20, 40 and 60°C)
155 for 24 h. The mixture obtained was filtered (Pobel glass plate, porosity 4, Madrid, Spain), the
156 crude lipidic extract was collected and the total volume fitted to a known volume (50 mL).
157 Then, this extract was characterized by determining the parameters indicated in Section 2.5.
158 In some of the experiments, the biomass residue was washed using 10 mL ethanol (96%
159 v/v)/g db, agitating for 15 min at 300 rpm. Subsequently, the mixture was filtered again and
160 the lipidic extract characterized in the same way as the first lipidic extract.

161 Some of the wet biomass samples (76 and 86 wt% water) were pretreated in just one
162 step by high-pressure homogenization at 500, 1000 and 1500 bar using a Panda Plus 2000
163 S.N. 8983 model homogenizer, purchased from GEA Niro Soavi S.p.A, (Parma, Italy).

164 The scaling up of the extraction process was carried out in 1 and 5 L glass reactors,
165 jacketed for temperature control and agitated at 300 rpm with a propeller stirrer (Eurostar
166 digital, IKA, Staufen, Germany) using 50-700 g of wet biomass and 0.6-2 L of ethanol (96%
167 v/v).

168

169 *2.3. Purification of the crude microalgal oil by hexane extraction*

170 For these experiments, the crude microalgal lipidic extract was obtained from the lyophilized
171 biomass using 40 mL ethanol (96% v/v)/g db (Table 2 B). Under these conditions, the SL
172 concentration in the ethanolic crude extract was 3.0 g SL/L. This concentration was decreased
173 to 1.5 g/L by dilution with ethanol (96% v/v) and then increased to 4.5 and 9.0 g SLs/L by
174 ethanol evaporation (96% v/v) in a vacuum rotary evaporator (Büchi R210, vacuum pump V-
175 700, vacuum controller V-850, Switzerland). Then, the water content of these lipidic extracts
176 was increased to 38% v/v by adding water. In this way, hydroethanolic solutions with SL
177 concentrations of 0.9, 1.9, 2.8 and 5.6 g/L were obtained for SL extraction with hexane. In a
178 typical experiment, 160 mL of water was added to 265 mL of crude microalgal extract to
179 obtain a hydroethanolic solution with 38% water v/v. Then, 75 mL of hexane was added (0.18
180 mL/mL hexane/hydroethanolic solution ratio), forming a biphasic system. Extraction was
181 performed in a 1 L glass reactor for 10 min at room temperature (20 °C) under a nitrogen
182 atmosphere, and agitated at 300 rpm. Following this, the mixture was decanted for 10 min and
183 the two phases were separated. The hydroethanolic phase was extracted three times more with
184 75 mL hexane in each of the extraction steps; a total of four hexane extracts were obtained.
185 The hexane extraction was also scaled up to a total volume of 2 L of hexane-hydroethanolic
186 mixture (a scaling up factor of 4). In each of the extraction steps (1 to 4), once the two phases
187 were separated, the hexane volume was adjusted to a known volume (100 mL) and an aliquot
188 was taken to determine the yield and purity of the extracted SLs (Section 2.5).

189

190 *2.4. Purification of SLs by crystallization in acetone at low temperature*

191 The purity of the SLs extracted with hexane was increased using an acetone crystallization
192 procedure based on the methods described by Rajam, Kumar, Sundaresan & Arumughan
193 (2005) and Vandana, Karuna, Vijayalakshmi & Prasad (2001). Firstly, the hexane was
194 evaporated in the vacuum rotary evaporator. Then 1 g of lipid extract (42 wt% SLs) was
195 mixed with 22 mL of acetone in topaz flasks and hermetically sealed with screw caps. These
196 flasks were placed in the orbital shaker at 50 °C and agitated at 200 rpm for 1 h to obtain a
197 homogeneous solution. The solution was then kept in a cold room at 7 °C for 24 h, after which
198 the supernatant and precipitate were separated by vacuum filtration at 7 °C. A supernatant
199 sample was taken for analysis to determine the SL, NSL, GL and PL recovery yields and the
200 SL purity.

201 All the extraction and purification experiments were carried out in triplicate and the
202 results were expressed as the arithmetic mean \pm the standard deviation.

203

204 *2.5. Analytical procedures*

205 *2.5.1. Determination of saponifiable lipids (SLs)*

206 The weight percentages of SLs (in terms of biomass dry weight) and the SL fatty acid
207 composition (the weight percentage of each fatty acid with respect to the total of fatty acids in
208 the biomass) (Table 1) of both *N. gaditana* biomass batches (Section 2.1) were determined by
209 direct transesterification of the lyophilized microalgal biomass, transforming all the SLs into
210 fatty acid methyl esters (FAMEs), which were then analyzed by gas chromatography (GC).
211 Also the amount of extracted SLs was determined by methylation and GC analysis of the
212 samples. Analysis was carried out in an Agilent Technology 6890N gas chromatograph (Santa
213 Clara, USA) equipped with a capillary column of fused silica OmegaWaxTM (0.25 mm \times 30

214 m, 0.25 μm standard film, Supelco, Bellefonte, PA, USA) and a flame ionization detector
215 (FID). A detailed description of the method and equipment is expounded in Jiménez Callejón
216 *et al.* (2014).

217 The SL yield in the extraction of crude microalgal oil using ethanol (96% v/v) was
218 calculated by equation (1):

$$220 \text{ Ethanol SL yield (wt\%)} = \frac{\text{amount of extracted SLs using ethanol}}{\text{total amount of SLs contained in the biomass}} 100 \quad (1)$$

221
222 The SL yield from the purification step following SL extraction with hexane from the
223 hydroethanolic solution was calculated by equation (2):

$$225 \text{ Hexane SL yield (wt\%)} = \frac{\text{amount of extracted SLs using hexane}}{\text{total amount of SLs contained in the hydroethanolic solution}} 100 \quad (2)$$

226
227 The SL yield from the purification step by crystallization in acetone was calculated
228 using equation (3):

$$230 \text{ Acetone SL yield (wt\%)} = \frac{\text{amount SLs in the acetone solution}}{\text{total amount of SLs contained in the previous hexane phase}} 100 \quad (3)$$

231
232 The global SL yield is the percentage of extracted and purified SL (as equivalent
233 FAMES) with respect to the total amount of SLs contained in the original biomass. It was
234 calculated using equation (4)

$$236 \text{ Global SL yield (wt\%)} = \frac{\text{ethanol SL yield}}{100} \frac{\text{hexane SL yield}}{100} \frac{\text{acetone SL yield}}{100} 100 \quad (4)$$

237

238 The SL purity is the weight percentage of SLs (determined by quantitative GC as
239 equivalent FAMES) with respect to the total amount of extract, determined by weighing, after
240 the complete removal of the solvent contained in the lipid extract. It was calculated using
241 equation (5)

242

$$243 \text{ SL purity (wt\%)} = \frac{\text{amount SLs determined by GC}}{\text{dry weight of extract}} 100 \quad (5)$$

244

245 All the analyses were carried out in triplicate and the results were expressed as the
246 arithmetic mean \pm the standard deviation.

247

248 *2.5.2. Determination of neutral saponifiable lipids (NSLs), glycolipids (GLs) and* 249 *phospholipids (PLs)*

250 The NSLs, GLs and PLs from the biomass samples were obtained by fractionation of the total
251 lipid dry extract, previously obtained following the Kochet (1978) method and described in
252 Macías-Sánchez *et al.* (2014) and Hita Peña *et al.* (2015). This fractionation was carried out
253 following the procedure also described in Jiménez Callejón *et al.* (2014) - basically it consists
254 of eluting the lipodic extract in a silica-gel cartridge (Sep-pak plus WAT020520, Waters
255 Corporations, Milford, MA) following the procedure of Kates (1986). Samples were eluted
256 with chloroform, acetone, and chloroform:methanol 85:15 v/v and methanol, with the NSLs,
257 GLs and PLs, respectively, being collected from each of these mobile phases. GC analysis of
258 all the fractions gave the percentages of NSLs, GLs and PLs with respect to the SLs and their
259 fatty acid profile. This lipid fractionation was also applied to lipid samples extracted with
260 ethanol (96% v/v) and acetone to determine the percentages and yields of each SL type.

261 The NSL, GL and PL yields in the extraction of SL using ethanol (96% v/v) and
262 acetone were calculated using equation (6):

263 Ethanol or acetone NSL, GL or PL yield (wt%) =

264
$$\frac{\text{amount of extracted NSLs, GL or PLs using ethanol or acetone}}{\text{total amount of NSLs, GL or PLs, respectively, contained in the original biomass or in the hexane phase respectively}} \times 100$$

265 (6)

266

267 The global NSL, GL and PL yields were calculated using equation (7):

268

269 Global NSL, GL or PL yield (wt%) =

270
$$\frac{\text{global SL yield (wt\%)} \times \text{percentage of NSL, GL or PL in the acetone solution (wt\%)}}{\text{percentage of NSL, GL or PL, respectively, contained in the biomass (wt\%)}} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

271

272 2.6. Energy consumption calculations

273 The energy consumption per unit mass of extracted SL for the different processes and
274 operational conditions was estimated as:

275
$$E \left(\frac{\text{MJ}}{\text{Kg extracted SL}} \right)$$

276
$$= \frac{\text{Energy (MJ)}}{\text{Wet biomass (86 wt\%)(Kg)}} \times \frac{1}{0.14 \times 0.12 \times \% \text{Ethanol SL yield} / 100}$$

277 Firstly, the energy consumption per unit mass of wet biomass (86 wt% water) was determined
278 taking into account the power of the equipment used and the time required for the operation.

279 Then, the dry biomass content (0.14 Kg dry biomass/Kg wet biomass), the SL content (0.12
280 Kg SL/Kg dry biomass, batch 1), and the ethanol SL yield obtained by the different extraction

281 conditions were considered. The freezing energy was calculated based on a freezer with a 247

282 KWh/year consumption, a 500 L capacity and a wet biomass freezing time of 24 hours. The

283 lyophilization energy was obtained from a freeze dryer with a 2200 W power and an 80 Kg

284 wet biomass capacity operating for 24 hours (Acién, Fernández, Magán & Molina, 2012). To

285 obtain the centrifugation energy required to reduce the water content to 76 wt%, we

286 considered a centrifuge with a power of 1200 W, operating for 10 minutes to separate 1 Kg of
287 wet biomass originally having an 86 wt% water content. For homogenization at 1500 bar, the
288 energy consumption was calculated for a 1850 W power and an experimental wet biomass
289 flow rate of around 9 L/h (Jiménez Callejón *et al.*, 2014). The agitation energy consumption
290 was estimated at 9 and 20 W per Kg (required to maintain a turbulent flow at 300 rpm) for the
291 wet biomass extractions, using 20 and 40 mL of ethanol /g db, respectively. For dry biomass
292 extractions, the power was 32 and 98 W per Kg dry biomass, respectively. These power
293 outputs were determined by the tank designs for extraction from 100 Kg of wet biomass (86
294 wt%), or the dry weight equivalent. The heating energy was calculated considering the
295 ethanol/biomass ratio and the extraction temperature. The energy for ethanol recovery prior to
296 SL purification by hexane extraction (the first ethanol recovery) was calculated taking into
297 account the need to obtain SL concentrations in the hydroethanolic solution (38% v/v water
298 content) of 5.6 g/L (Section 3.3.1). In the case of extractions from dry biomass, this was
299 calculated considering only the heat capacity and latent heat of the ethanol. When the
300 extractions were performed on wet biomass, ethanol-water mixtures were obtained, and the
301 ethanol recovery energy was calculated for a discontinuous distillation. For each of the
302 operational conditions, the separation time required was estimated based on the distillation
303 equipment having a power output of 1700 W. The energy for the second ethanol recovery was
304 estimated under the same conditions until a 4 mol% ethanol residue was obtained.

305

306 **3. Results and discussion**

307 *3.1. Lipidic composition of the microalgal biomass*

308 Table 1 shows the SL content of the two microalgal batches used in this work, their fatty acid
309 compositions, the contents of NSLs, GLs and PLs and the fatty acid profile of these lipidic
310 species. Batch 2 contained a higher percentage of SLs (21.6 wt% db) than batch 1 (12.0 wt%),

311 basically due to a higher NSL content (reserve lipids) (17.2 wt%, batch 2 vs. 5.4 wt% db,
312 batch 1). This meant that 45.0 and 79.5 wt% of SLs in batches 1 and 2, respectively, were
313 NSLs, the rest being polar SL lipids (glycolipids, GLs, and phospholipids, PLs). Regarding
314 the fatty acid profile, batch 1 presented a higher PUFA content: 37.2 wt% of fatty acids vs.
315 16.9 wt% in batch 2. In any case, due to the differences between the SL content, the PUFA
316 content of biomass dry weight was not very different: 4.5 wt% and 3.7 wt% PUFAs of
317 biomass dry weight for batches 1 and 2, respectively. These PUFAs are mainly located in the
318 polar lipids (structural lipids), which is more evident in the batch 2 biomass, where the NSLs
319 contained 10.9 wt% of PUFAs whilst the GLs and PLs contained 32.7 and 45.7 wt% of
320 PUFAs, respectively. This differing lipidic composition is a consequence of the different
321 culture conditions of the two microalgal batches (Section 2.1, San Pedro *et al.*, 2013).

322

323 *3.2. Extraction of crude microalgal oil using ethanol (96% v/v)*

324 *3.2.1. Influence of the wet microalgal biomass water content and the ethanol (96%)/biomass* 325 *ratio*

326 Figure 1 A shows the SL yields obtained using different ethanol (96% v/v)/equivalent dry
327 biomass (db) ratios (5-60 mL/g db) as well as microalgal biomasses containing different water
328 contents (lyophilized biomass and wet biomass with 76 and 86 wt% water). This figure shows
329 that the SL yield was higher, the higher the ethanol/biomass ratio and the lower the water
330 content. Using lyophilized biomass, 92.3 wt% of SLs were extracted with only 20 mL
331 ethanol/g db. However, using wet biomass containing 76.0 wt% water, it was necessary to
332 double and triple the ethanol amount (40 and 60 mL/g db) to recover 86.9 and 98.3 wt% of
333 SLs, respectively. Using biomass containing 86 wt% water, the highest SL recovery was 82.1
334 wt% using 60 mL/g db. On the other hand, handling this wet biomass was easy since it is a
335 fluid suspension at room temperature; in contrast, the 76 wt% water biomass is a dense paste

336 that is difficult to manage. Similar results have been obtained by other authors. For example,
 337 Angles, Jaouen, Pruvost & Marchal (2017) compared wet and dry lipid extraction from
 338 *Nannochloropsis* sp. using the Bligh and Dyers system (chloroform:methanol, 2:1); they
 339 found that the presence of water in the wet biomass reduced the amount of extracted lipids by
 340 50% compared to the dry biomass. Yang, Xiang, Sun, Wu, Li & Long (2014) demonstrated
 341 the solvent/biomass ratio to be an important variable in the extraction of lipids. These authors
 342 tested lipid extraction using ethanol from wet *Picochlorum* sp. microalgal biomass (90%
 343 water). In the study, the central composite design was applied to investigate the optimum lipid
 344 extraction conditions - the results revealed that the solvent to biomass ratio exerted the largest
 345 effect on lipid extraction efficiency, followed by the extraction time and the temperature.
 346 Using 5 mL ethanol/g wet biomass (50 mL/g db) at room temperature for 37 min, a lipid
 347 extraction yield of 33% (dry weight) was obtained; this is equal to the lipid extraction yield
 348 achieved using the Bligh-Dyer method.

Fig. 1 A. Extraction of saponifiable lipids from *N. gaditana* biomass with ethanol. Influence of the biomass water content and the ethanol (96% v/v)/biomass ratio (mL ethanol/g dry biomass (db)) on the saponifiable lipid (SL) extraction yield (equation (1)). *Operational*

conditions: □ 86 wt% water biomass, ■ 76 wt% water biomass and ■ lyophilized biomass; all the extractions were carried out at 20 °C for 24 h, at 200 rpm using batch 1 of biomass (Table 1). Data are shown as mean ± SD, n = 3.

349 The extraction tests shown in Figure 1 A were carried out with a 24 h extraction time.
350 Extraction tests performed with 76 wt% water biomass and 20 mL ethanol/g db for longer
351 extraction times (48, 72 and 96 h) did not significantly increase the SL extraction yields
352 (74.0-75.5 wt%, similar to the 73.9 wt% obtained at 24 h; Fig. 1 A). However, decreasing the
353 extraction time to 7 h reduced the SL extraction yield to 63.1 wt% (data not shown). In
354 addition, Ramírez Fajardo *et al.* (2007) observed that SL recovery from the microalga
355 *Phaedactylum tricornutum* at room temperature increased in line with the extraction time but
356 remained constant above 20 h.

357 Washing the biomass residue coming from the extraction of 76 wt% water biomass
358 with 20 mL ethanol/g db (73.9 wt% SLs yield; Fig. 1 A) with 10 mL ethanol/g db for 15 min,
359 increased the SL yield by only 7.1 wt%.

360

361 3.2.2. *Influence of high-pressure homogenization*

362 It is common to carry out pretreatments on the microalgal biomass to provoke cell rupture and
363 increase the lipid extraction yield. The high pressure homogenization of biomass disrupts the
364 microalgal cell, facilitating the access of extracting solvent to the SLs contained in the cells
365 and increasing the SL extraction yield. This pretreatment has advantages, such as easy
366 scaling-up and low heat generation; thus, there is only a low risk of thermal degradation
367 (Halim *et al.*, 2012; Samarasinghe, Fernando, Lacey & Faulkner, 2012). Figure 1 B shows
368 that in all the cases, SL yield increased with the pretreatment and the homogenization
369 pressure, which we had already observed in our laboratory when extracting SLs with hexane

370 (Jiménez Callejón *et al.*, 2014). Figure 1 B shows that the homogenization of 86 wt% water
371 biomass at 1500 bar allows one to increase the SL recovery (with 20 mL ethanol/g db) from
372 50.3 to 79.9 wt%. This SL yield (79.9 wt%) is of the order obtained with 40 and 60 mL
373 ethanol/g db from non-homogenized biomass (Figure 1 A), which means that this
374 pretreatment could be used as an alternative that reduces the solvent amount. Homogenization
375 is less effective when the extraction conditions give relatively high SL yields, as with 76 wt%
376 water biomass-20 mL ethanol/g db and with 86 wt% water biomass-60 mL ethanol/g db.

377 Mulchandami, Kar & Singhal (2015) likewise observed a lipid recovery increase from
378 *Chlorella saccharophila* when the biomass was homogenized at 200-1000 bar (2-10 passes)
379 as a pretreatment. At a pressure of 800 bar, which was found to be optimal, 72 wt% of lipids
380 was recovered when compared to the control. Also, the number of passes at 800 bar were
381 optimized - they found that for ten passes, 89.9 wt% of lipid could be recovered during the t-
382 butanol phase. The high extraction efficiency observed in the ethanol method might be closely
383 related to the microalgal cell morphology, particularly that of the cell walls. For some
384 microalgae, lipids can be easily extracted without any prior cell disruption, whereas for others
385 that are enveloped by tough cell walls, several assisted extraction techniques may be required
386 to obtain a high lipid extraction yield. Yang *et al.* (2014, 2015) extracted lipids from the
387 microalgae *Chlorella* sp. and *Picochlorum* sp. using ethanol; these microalgae have relatively
388 thin cell walls, which can be weakened or disrupted by ethanol. For this reason, there was no
389 cell wall resistance, and the lipids were released from the cells, resulting in high extraction
390 efficiency.

Fig. 1 B. Extraction of saponifiable lipids from *N. gaditana* biomass with ethanol. Influence of the high-pressure homogenization of biomass on the saponifiable lipid (SL) extraction yield (equation (1)). *Operational conditions:* □ 76 wt% water biomass, 20 mL ethanol (96%)/g db, ■ 86 wt% water biomass, 20 mL ethanol (96%)/g db, ■ 86 wt% water biomass, 60 mL ethanol (96%)/g dry biomass; at 20 °C for 24 h at 200 rpm using batch 1 of biomass (Table 1) in all the experiments. Data are shown as mean \pm SD, n = 3.

391

392 3.2.3. Influence of the extraction temperature

393 Although our goal was SL extraction under mild operational conditions (working at room

394 temperature, at around 20-25 °C), experiments at higher temperatures were carried out to

395 study the possibility of reducing the amount of extractant solvent or the extraction time.

396 Figure 1 C shows that the SL extraction yield increased along with the extraction temperature

397 (operational conditions a and b, applied to biomass batch 1; Fig. 1 C). With only 20 mL

398 ethanol/g db (conditions a), the SL recovery was low, even at 60 °C (66.2 wt%). With 40 mL

399 ethanol/g db (conditions b), SL recovery was 92.7 wt% at 60 °C. However, at this

400 temperature, it is possible to reduce the extraction time from 24 h to 0.5 h (conditions c) with

401 only a small SL yield decrease (90.5 wt%). However, when SL extraction was carried out

402 under the latter conditions using biomass batch 2 (21.6 wt% SLs of biomass dry weight; Table
 403 1), only a very low SL extraction yield was achieved (36.6 wt%, conditions d; Fig. 1 C). In
 404 addition to reasons related to the different biomass composition, this decreased yield might be
 405 due to the lower ethanol/SL ratio used, since the batch 2 biomass had a higher SL content. To
 406 obtain similar yields to those of batch 1, it was necessary to double the ethanol/biomass ratio
 407 (80 mL/g db, conditions e; Fig. 1 C) with respect to that used for batch 1. Taking into account
 408 the SL contents of batch 1 (12.0 wt% SLs) and 2 (21.6 wt% SLs), similar ethanol (96%
 409 v/v)/SL ratios were used with the ethanol/biomass ratios of 40 for batch 1 (condition c), and
 410 80 mL/g for batch 2 (condition d). With this latter ethanol/biomass ratio, a 92.8 wt% SL yield
 411 was obtained (Figure 1 C) from batch 2.
 412

Fig. 1 C. Extraction of saponifiable lipids from *N. gaditana* wet biomass (86 wt% water) with ethanol. Influence of the temperature on the saponifiable lipid (SL) extraction yield (equation (1)). *Operational conditions:* a: □ Batch 1, 20 mL/g dry biomass (db) (50 mL ethanol), 24 h and 200 rpm. b: ■ Batch 1, 40 mL/g db (50 mL ethanol), 24 h and 200 rpm. c: ■ Batch 1, 40 mL/g db (50 mL ethanol), 0.5 h and 200 rpm. d: ▨ Batch 2, 40 mL/g db (280 mL ethanol), 0.5 h and 300 rpm. e: ▩ Batch 2, 80 mL/g db (560 mL ethanol), 0.5 h and 300 rpm. Data are shown as mean \pm SD, n = 3.

413

414 3.2.4. *Optimal conditions, scaling up and lipidic composition of crude microalgal oil*

415

416 From the previous experiments (Sections 3.2.1 to 3.2.3) it was observed that, for the
417 same biomass batch, SL yields similar to or higher than 80 wt% could be achieved under
418 different condition combinations (see Figures 1 A to C). To choose amongst these conditions,
419 the energy consumption per unit mass of extracted SL was estimated and compared (Table 2
420 A). We found that when the ethanol recovery is not considered, the minimum energy
421 consumption clearly corresponded to the following conditions: 86 wt% water biomass, no
422 homogenization, 40 mL/g db for 0.5 h at 60 °C (90.5 wt% SL yield; Fig. 1 C, extraction
423 condition d in Table 2 A). This lower energy consumption (47.7 MJ/Kg of extracted SL)
424 resulted from only using a centrifugation step to harvest the biomass (wet biomass with 86
425 wt% water; Section 2.1), the non-homogenization of the biomass and, above all, the short
426 extraction time (0.5 h); although a relatively high temperature (60 °C) was required. Macías-
427 Sánchez *et al.* (2014) also found that the extraction time (0.5 or 24 h) increased the energy
428 consumption much more than the temperature did (60 or 20°C, respectively). If one wishes to
429 extract at room temperature (i.e. milder conditions), where extraction is carried out without
430 heating, the conditions with the lowest energy consumption per unit mass of extracted SL
431 (113 MJ/Kg) are: 86 wt% water biomass, homogenization at 1500 bar, 20 mL/g db for 24 h at
432 20 °C (79.9 wt% SL yield; Fig. 1 C, extraction condition c in Table 2 A). The conditions
433 described above (extraction conditions c and d, Table 2 A) show a lower energy consumption
434 because biomass lyophilization is not necessary and this step supposes an energy consumption
435 of around 142-153 MJ/Kg of extracted SL (Table 2 A). Lardon, Helias, Sialve, Steyer &
436 Bernard (2009) also described a drying process energy consumption of 90.32 MJ per Kg for
437 biodiesel obtained from microalgae, signifying around 85% of the dry method costs to
438 produce biodiesel.

439 However, when the ethanol (a water-miscible solvent) recovery is considered, energy
440 consumption increases significantly. The most favorable conditions are obtained using
441 lyophilized biomass (conditions a and b in Table 2 A) especially under condition b (592.7
442 MJ/Kg of extracted SL, 92.3% of SL yield), which only used 20 mL ethanol/g dry biomass
443 versus 40 mL/g under condition a. Although the consumptions for the second ethanol
444 recovery (recovery following SL purification by hexane extraction; Section 3.3.1) are quite
445 similar under all extraction conditions (358.2 - 364.7 MJ/Kg of extracted SL), there are
446 important differences in the energy consumption for the first ethanol recovery (55.0 - 901.3
447 MJ/Kg of extracted SL), which was lower when lyophilized biomass was used (conditions a
448 and b, Table 2 A). This is due to the presence of water in the first ethanol recovery when wet
449 biomass was used (conditions c, d and e, Table 2 A), thus requiring energy-intensive
450 distillation to recover the ethanol; this operation increased the energy consumption to 881-901
451 MJ/Kg of extracted SL for the first ethanol recovery when 40 mL ethanol/g db were used
452 (conditions d and e, Table 2 A) versus 176 MJ/Kg required when using dry biomass
453 (condition a, Table 2 A). Therefore, the costs of recovering ethanol using intensive distillation
454 cancel out the advantage of working with wet biomass, in which the lyophilization costs are
455 avoided. In any case, Table 2 A shows that this balance (lyophilization versus ethanol
456 recovery costs) depends on the ethanol/biomass ratio used.

457

458 Accordingly, some of the previously carried out experiments were scaled up to higher
459 extraction volumes. Table 2 B shows the good large-scale reproducibility of the SL yields
460 achieved beforehand at the small scale. Also NSL, GL and PL yields were determined. Table
461 2 B shows that when using wet biomass, the NSL recoveries were higher than those for PLs
462 and GLs (condition c in Table 2 A). In this way, for a 78.2 wt% SL yield (obtained from the
463 homogenized 86 wt% water biomass), 97.3 wt% of NSLs were recovered whereas the GL and

464 PL yields were 59.2 and 69.1 wt%, respectively. A similar result was likewise observed by
465 Ryckebosch *et al.* (2013) for the extraction of lipids from lyophilized *N. gaditana* biomass
466 using ethanol - for a lipid extraction yield of 52.6%, the recoveries of NSLs, GLs and PLs
467 were 78.1, 27.4 and 41.5%, respectively. This is the result not only of the high solvent
468 capacity of ethanol, which solves neutral and polar lipids, but also to the greater difficulty in
469 solving these latter lipids, since neutral lipids are relatively free in the cells while polar lipids
470 form complexes with some neutral lipids and also with proteins in the cell membrane (Halim
471 at al., 2012; Ryckebosch *et al.*, 2014).

472

473 *3.3. Purification of crude microalgal oil*

474 In addition to SLs, the crude microalgal oil extracted using ethanol contains other substances
475 such as proteins, carbohydrates and other lipidic and non-lipidic compounds. Under the
476 conditions used in this work, the SLs extracted using ethanol are 20-22% of the extracts' dry
477 weight; for this reason we tried to increase their purity. The ethanol SL extracts were obtained
478 with different SL concentrations, depending on the extraction conditions; primarily, the
479 ethanol/biomass ratio and the wet biomass water content. These concentrations were in the
480 1.5 - 4 g/L range, which is important in the following purification step.

481

482 *3.3.1. SL purification by hexane extraction*

483 The purification of the SLs extracted with ethanol (96% v/v) can be performed by adding
484 water and hexane to form a biphasic system, recovering the SLs with higher purity in the
485 hexane phase (Ramírez Fajardo *et al.*, 2007). Hence, the water content of the ethanolic SL
486 extracts was increased to 38% v/v by adding water. In this way, the immiscibility of the
487 hydroethanolic and hexane phases was increased and the SL equilibrium distribution between
488 the two phases was displaced towards the hexane phase; this also contributes to decreasing the

489 hexane/hydroethanolic solution ratio required to extract the SLs (Ibáñez, Robles, Molina,
490 Giménez, Carstens & Esteban, 1998). Figure 2 shows the SL recoveries in the hexane phase
491 after performing four extraction steps on the hydroethanolic solutions (38% v/v water content)
492 at several SL concentrations in the hydroethanolic solution (0.9-5.6 g/L). This figure shows
493 how the SL extraction yield in the first extraction step is considerably higher because of the
494 higher SL concentration in the hydroethanolic solution - performing SL extraction from a
495 solution with an SL concentration of 5.6 g SLs/L using a single hexane extraction, 94.3 wt%
496 of SLs were recovered, whereas from an SL concentration of 0.9 g SLs/L, only 50.7 wt% of
497 SLs were extracted in a single extraction step. This 94.3 wt% yield of SLs contained in the
498 hydroethanolic solution (equation (2)) means around a 93.8 wt% yield of SLs contained in the
499 biomass. Figure 2 shows that, in the extractions at concentrations between 0.9 and 2.8 g SL/L,
500 around 9-15 wt% of SLs (with respect to the SLs contained in the hydroethanolic solution)
501 were recovered in the second extraction step; however a higher extraction step amount did not
502 significantly increase the SL yield (Fig. 2). Similar yields were obtained by scaling up the
503 hexane extraction to a total hexane-hydroethanolic volume in the solution mixture of 2 L.
504 Therefore, when carrying out hexane extraction on SL hydroethanolic extracts, it is important
505 to use as concentrated a solution mixture as possible. After hexane extraction under these
506 conditions, the SL purity increased from the initial 20-22 wt% to 42 wt% (SL/hexane extract
507 dry weight; equation (5)). This SL purity is still lower than that obtained (60-63 wt%)
508 extracting SLs directly from homogenized wet biomass (86 wt% water) with hexane (Jiménez
509 Callejón *et al.*, 2014). However, the maximum SL yield achieved using hexane instead of
510 ethanol (from microalgal biomass batch 2) was around 57.0 wt%, due to hexane's limited
511 capacity to extract polar lipids from the wet biomass (Jiménez Callejón *et al.*, 2014). On the
512 other hand, we did not observe significant differences between the fatty acid profiles obtained

513 in the hexanic extract and those of the SLs contained in the hydroethanolic extracts at the
514 different SL concentrations tested (0.9-5.6 g/L).

515

Fig. 2. Extraction of saponifiable lipids contained in the hydroethanolic solution with hexane: influence of the concentration in the hydroethanolic solution (C_{HE} , g saponifiable lipid (SL)/L) on the SL yield by hexane extraction (with respect to the SL contained in the hydroethanolic solution, equation (2)). *Operational conditions:* SL extraction with a hexane/hydroethanolic solution (38% v/v water) ratio of 0.18 v/v (75 mL hexane/425 mL hydroethanolic solutions (38% v/v water) in the steps: 1□, 2■, 3▨ and 4■. Agitation at 300 rpm for 10 min. Data are shown as mean \pm SD, n = 3.

516

517 3.3.2. Oil purification by crystallization in acetone

518 In the previous hexane extraction step, the microalgal SLs were recovered with hexane SL

519 yields (equation (2)) of 99.5 and 99.1 wt% from hydroethanolic extracts coming from

520 biomass batches 1 and 2, respectively. However, the purity of these extracts was only 42.1

521 wt% and 42.4 wt%, respectively. To increase their purity, these hexane extracts were

522 subjected to a new crystallization in acetone purification step. Table 3 shows the SL purities

523 and yields achieved after this purification step, which was applied to hexane extracts from

524 both biomass batches. We can observe that the SL purity was increased from 42.1-42.4 wt%
525 to 95.2-96.0 wt% (SL/dry extract weight; equation (5)), with high SL recoveries (70.1-85.1
526 wt%, with respect to the SLs contained in the hexane extract; equation (3)). The result
527 demonstrates the suitability of this SL purification method. The higher SL yield achieved with
528 the SLs in batch 2 (85.1 vs. 70.1 wt% from batch 1) fits with the higher NSL content of batch
529 2 (Table 1) since these NSLs remain solubilized in the acetone, while the precipitate is rich in
530 PLs and waxes (Rajam *et al.*, 2005; Huynh, Kasim & Ju, 2010). Table 3 also shows the
531 distribution of purified SLs into NSLs, GLs and PLs and, as mentioned before, the recovered
532 SLs are richer in NSLs than the corresponding original biomasses (Table 1); even these
533 recovered SLs do not contain PLs because, again as mentioned before, these PLs were
534 removed due to their insolubility in acetone at low temperature. Therefore, the SLs obtained
535 are very rich in NSLs, especially those obtained from batch 2 (93.6 wt%), which were initially
536 richer in these lipids (79.5 wt%; Table 1). To illustrate these results more clearly, Table 3 also
537 shows the yields obtained with respect to the total SLs contained in the original biomass
538 (equation (7)); one can observe the high NSL yields (98.8 and 92,2 wt%) compared to GL
539 (67.6 and 33.9 wt%) and, above all, to PL yields (0%).

540 With respect to the PUFA and EPA contents in the final SL concentrate, Table 4
541 shows the fatty acid profiles of the final SL concentrates obtained from both batches after the
542 acetone crystallization step; this can be compared to the fatty acid profile of the original
543 biomass batches (Table 1). The table shows that biomass batches 1 and 2 contain 25.3 and
544 11.1 wt% of EPA, respectively. These EPA contents decrease slightly to 25.0 and 8.1 wt% in
545 the SL concentrates obtained from batches 1 and 2, respectively (Table 4); this is due to the
546 higher PUFA content of the polar lipids, which precipitates in the acetone crystallization step.

547

548 **4. Conclusions**

549 This research provides a method for obtaining lipid extracts with high purity. Under
550 optimized conditions, which consider the energy consumption (including solvent recovery),
551 92.3 wt% of SLs were extracted from dry biomass using 20 mL ethanol (96%)/g db, for 24 h
552 at 20 °C. The purity of these extracted SLs (20-22 wt%) was increased to 42 wt% by hexane
553 extraction, and then to 95.2-96.0 wt% by acetone crystallization. The SL global yield of this
554 process was 69.4-78.3 wt%. These SLs are constituted mostly of NSLs (64.2-93.6 wt%). The
555 SL yields, purities, SL type (neutral, GLs and PLs) and final PUFA content also depend on
556 the microalgal lipid profile (i.e., on the culture condition).

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Declarations

There are no potential financial or other interests that could be perceived to influence the outcomes of the research. No conflicts, informed consent, human or animal rights are applicable. All authors confirmed the manuscript’s authorship and agreed to submit it for peer review.

Author contributions

All authors have contributed to the manuscript. All authors contributed to the research design, data analyses, and all authors have revised, edited and approved the final manuscript. The experimental work was done by María José Jiménez Callejón.

Table 1

Saponifiable lipid (SL), neutral saponifiable lipid (NSL), glycolipid (GL) and phospholipid (PL) contents (wt% of dry biomass, db) for batches 1 and 2 of the microalga *N. gaditana* along with the fatty acid composition (wt% of total fatty acids in each lipidic species, sum of saturated and monounsaturated fatty acids, SMUFAs, and sum of polyunsaturated fatty acids, PUFAs) of the SLs, NSLs, GLs and PLs of both batches.

Lipidic class	Microalgal batch 1				Microalgal batch 2			
	SL	NSL	GL	PL	SL	NSL	GL	PL
wt% db	12.0 ±	5.4 ±	4.4 ±	2.2 ±	21.6 ±	17.2 ±	3.2 ±	1.2 ±
	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.3
wt% of total SL		45.0 ±	36.7 ±	18.3 ±		79.5 ±	14.8 ±	5.7 ±
		0.3	0.3	0.0		0.3	0.1	0.2
Fatty acid	wt% of total fatty acid in each one of the lipidic species							
14:0	6.9 ±	6.7 ±	8.8 ±	3.6 ±	8.8 ±	9.5 ±	8.2 ±	3.8 ±
	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1
16:0	25.8 ±	25.8 ±	26.0 ±	25.3 ±	25.8 ±	28.4 ±	20.5 ±	19.2 ±
	0.0	1.5	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2
16:1n7	20.5 ±	21.0 ±	19.9 ±	20.6 ±	36.6 ±	42.9 ±	20.6 ±	18.4 ±
	0.2	1.2	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2
18:1n9	3.9 ±	3.4 ±	1.8 ±	9.3 ±	4.8 ±	4.8 ±	11.1 ±	12.3 ±
	0.5	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0
18:2n6	4.4 ±	3.2 ±	2.6 ±	11.1 ±	2.3 ±	1.4 ±	1.5 ±	9.4 ±
	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1
18:3n3	2.8 ±	5.7 ±	0.6 ±	0.0 ±	0.1 ±	0.6 ±	0.0 ±	0.0 ±
	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
20:4n6	4.8 ±	4.5 ±	3.3 ±	8.4 ±	3.4 ±	2.1 ±	4.1 ±	14.3 ±
	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1
20:5n3	25.3 ±	20.8 ±	32.6 ±	21.5 ±	11.1 ±	6.8 ±	27.1 ±	22.0 ±
	0.1	1.4	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.6
Others	5.6 ±	8.8 ±	4.4 ±	0.2 ±	7.0 ±	3.4 ±	6.9 ±	0.5 ±
	0.3	0.4	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.7	0.8
∑ SMUFAs	58.6 ±	59.8 ±	56.9 ±	58.9 ±	76.9 ±	86.6 ±	62.7 ±	53.7 ±
	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.3

Σ PUFAs	37.2 \pm	34.2 \pm	39.1 \pm	41.0 \pm	16.9 \pm	10.9 \pm	32.7 \pm	45.7 \pm
	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.2	0.3
wt% PUFAs	4.5 \pm	1.8 \pm	1.7 \pm	0.9 \pm	3.7 \pm	2.0 \pm	1.1 \pm	0.6 \pm
on db	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.2

Data are shown as mean \pm SD, n = 3.

Table 2

Saponifiable lipid (SL) extraction process from *N. gaditana* lyophilized and wet microalgal biomass (batch 1) with ethanol (96% v/v): (A) Comparison of energy consumption under different operational conditions. (B) Scaling up of the extraction process: SL, neutral saponifiable lipid (NSL), glycolipid (GL) and phospholipid (PL) yields.

(A)					
Extraction conditions	a	b	c	d	e
Ethanol SL yield, wt %	99.5	92.3	79.9	90.5	86.9
Process	Energy consumption: E, MJ/Kg extracted SL				
Freezing	0.3	0.3			
Lyophilization	142.1	153.2			
Centrifugation					50.3
Homogenization			55.1		
Agitation	70.9	25.0	57.9	2.4	118.4
Heating				45.3	
Sum	213.3	178.5	113.0	47.7	168.7
First ethanol recovery ¹	176.1	55.0	337.4	881.5	901.3
Second ethanol recovery ²	358.8	359.2	360.2	358.2	364.7
Sum (with ethanol recovery)	748.2	592.7	810.6	1287.4	1434.7

Extraction conditions: a) Dry biomass, 20 °C, 24 h, 40 mL/g db (Fig. 1 A). b) Dry biomass, 20 °C, 24 h, 20 mL/g db (Fig. 1 A). c) Wet biomass (86 wt%) homogenized at 1500 bar, 20 °C, 24 h, 20 mL/g db (Fig. 1 B). d) Wet biomass (86 wt%), 60 °C, 0.5 h, 40 mL/g db (Fig. 1 C). e) Wet biomass (76 wt%), 20 °C, 24 h, 40 mL/g db (Fig. 1 A).

¹ Recovery prior to SL purification by hexane extraction (section 3.3.1). ² Recovery after to SL purification by hexane extraction.

(B)

Biomass, g (wt% water)	Ethanol, L (mL/g db)	Yield on each one of the lipidic species, wt%			
		SL ¹	NSL ²	GL ²	PL ²
50 (0) ^a	2 (40)	99.5 ± 0.1	99.9 ± 0.1	99.3 ± 0.2	99.1 ± 0.3
714 (86) ^c	2 (20)	78.2 ± 0.2	97.3 ± 0.4	59.2 ± 0.3	69.1 ± 0.2

¹ Equation (1). ² Equation (6).

^a 20 °C, 24 h, 300 rpm (99.5 wt% SL yield at lower scale, Fig. 1 A); ^c Homogenized biomass at 1500 bar, 20 °C, 24 h, 300 rpm (79.9 wt% SL yield at lower scale, Fig. 1 B).

Data are shown as mean ± SD, n = 3.

Table 3

Purification of saponifiable lipids (SLs)^a from both biomass batches by crystallization in acetone: SL purities (equation (5)) and yields (equation (3)), percentages of neutral saponifiable lipids (NSLs), glycolipids (GLs) and phospholipid (PLs) and global yields of SLs, NSLs, GLs and PLs with respect to the contents in the original biomasses (equations (4) and (7)).

	Batch 1	Batch 2
SL purity (wt%)	95.2 ± 0.3	96.0 ± 0.2
SL yield (wt%) ^b	70.1 ± 0.1	85.1 ± 0.1
Composition in lipid species of the SLs (wt%) ^c		
NSLs	64.2 ± 0.7	93.6 ± 0.7
GLs	35.8 ± 0.7	6.4 ± 0.7
PLs	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0
Global yield (wt%) ^d		
SLs	69.4 ± 0.1 ^e	78.3 ± 0.2 ^f
NSLs	98.8 ± 0.3 ^e	92.2 ± 0.1 ^f
GLs	67.6 ± 0.4 ^e	33.9 ± 0.3 ^f
PLs	0.0 ± 0.0 ^e	0.0 ± 0.0 ^f

^a SLs previously purified by four hexane extraction steps from a hydroethanolic solution (38% v/v water) with 2.8 g SLs/L (section 3.3.1.); SL purity 42.1 wt% (batch 1) and 42.4 wt% (batch 2).

^b SL yield with respect to the SLs contained in the hexane extract (equation (3)).

^c Weight percentages of total SLs.

^d Global yields with respect to the SLs in the original biomass after the steps of: 1) Extraction of crude oil with ethanol (96% v/v), 2) SL extraction with hexane from the hydroethanolic extract (38% v/v water) and 3) crystallization in acetone (equations (4) and (7)).

^e Yield obtained taking as crude microalgal oil that extracted from lyophilized biomass with 40 mL ethanol/g db (Table 2 B).

^f Yield obtained taking as crude microalgal oil that extracted at 60 °C, 0.5 h and 80 mL/ g db (Figure 1 C, operational conditions e).

Data are shown as mean ± SD, n = 3.

Table 4

Fatty acid composition of saponifiable lipids, SLs (wt% of total fatty acids) in the final concentrate (SLs purified by crystallization in acetone) from batches 1 and 2.

Fatty acid	Batch 1	Batch 2
14:0	7.4 ± 0.1	9.4 ± 0.3
16:0	25.9 ± 0.1	27.9 ± 0.0
16:1n7	20.5 ± 0.3	41.5 ± 0.3
18:1n9	2.8 ± 0.3	5.2 ± 0.6
18:2n6	3.0 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.1
18:3n3	3.9 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.0
20:4n6	4.1 ± 0.2	2.2 ± 0.1
20:5n3	25.0 ± 0.1	8.1 ± 0.4
Others	5.5 ± 0.5	2.7 ± 0.6

^a *Operational conditions*: see Table 3.

Data are shown as mean ± SD, n = 3.

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